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**LINGUOCULTUROLOGY AS A LEADING BRANCH OF MODERN
LINGUISTICS**

Annotation: In order to develop the knowledge of linguistics and language skills, one is eager to be aware of all branches of linguistics and the important factors of theirs. Learning the items that are relevant to the culture of this or that nationality on the behalf of linguistic norms, comparing or contrasting them with the own culture can be concluded with full of information, which call most people's attention. And therefore one of the branch of linguistics called Linguoculturology is worthy of studying.

Key words: linguistics, culture, cultural linguistics, language, interaction, concept, comparison.

It is obvious that people are alive with communication and the role of a language in human's life is irreplaceable and all the factors of a language or some languages are considered in Linguistics as it is called a scientific study of a human language because of entailing a comprehensive, systematic, objective, and precise analysis of all aspects of language, particularly its nature and structure. Linguistics of the 21st century actively develops a direction in which the language is considered as the cultural code of the nation, and not just a tool of communication and knowledge. The fundamental foundations of this approach were laid by the works W.V. Humboldt, A.A. Potebnya as well as lots of other scientists all over the world and on this issue W. Humboldt said: "The boundaries of the language of my nation mean the boundaries of my worldview." [1]

It goes without saying, that the language of this or that nation is half of its culture as the language contains a lot of crucial things showing them in conversations, attitudes to other human beings and in other circumstances with various views. If the traditional way of understanding the problem of the interaction of language and culture is to try to solve linguistic problems using some ideas about culture, then in our work we study the ways in which language embodies in its units, stores and transmits culture. [2]

The main directions in modern linguistics, which are being formed within the framework of it, are cognitive linguistics and linguoculturology, which should be "focused on the cultural factor in the language and on the linguistic factor in the person" [3] More over, there are a range of branches of linguistics that are responsible for various issues of languages and one of them is linguoculturology.

ПЕДАГОГИКА И ПСИХОЛОГИЯ В СОВРЕМЕННОМ МИРЕ: ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ И ПРАКТИЧЕСКИЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ

Linguoculturology studies language as a phenomenon of culture. This is a certain vision of the world through the prism of the national language, when the language acts as an exponent of a special national mentality. All linguistics is permeated with cultural and historical content, because language has its subject, which is a condition, basis and product of culture.

Linguoculturology (in some sources are given as cultural linguistics) is a branch of modern linguistics studying language as a phenomenon of culture. Differ from other existing directions, the subject of modern linguoculturology is the study of the cultural semantics of linguistic signs, which is formed by the interaction of two different codes - language and culture as significant parts of this branch.

Cultural linguistics is a branch of linguistics that arose at the intersection of linguistics and cultural studies and explores the manifestations of the culture of the people, which are reflected and entrenched in the language.[4]

A scientist probably prefers to study the interaction of language and culture in the exact sphere, without a historical view of the problem. This approach leads to the consideration of linguoculturology as a branch of ethnolinguistics as well as comparing and contrasting culture of two or more than two nationalities are the main tasks of this subject. All and all, Linguoculturology is an approach towards culture of this or that nation with the point of a language and linguistic norms.

Well, more and more people are keen on learning about culture of a country, comparing the similarities and differences of culture or contrasting that within nationalities with linguistic points of view including any kind of phrases, phraseological units, concepts, idioms, contexts and others are worthy of studying about.

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